

The ideational robustness of liberal democracy in the wake of the pandemic: comparing the Danish and Swedish cases

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic sparked unprecedented political responses dramatically affecting societies, markets, and the lives of individuals. Under great uncertainty and turbulent conditions, governments adopted far-reaching political interventions to curb the pandemic. These interventions might therefore be expected to challenge key ideas underpinning liberal democracy. We analyze and compare how the political interventions seeking to curb the spread of the coronavirus in Denmark and Sweden challenged and possibly adapted three key ideas underpinning liberal democracy, namely, constitutionality, parliamentarism, and public responsiveness. When ideas are adapted in ways that advance their ability to stay relevant when faced with turbulence, we understand them as robust. Our study found both similarities and differences between the two countries. The idea of constitutionality was challenged in Denmark but remained robust in Sweden. The idea of parliamentarism appeared robust in both countries, whereas the idea of public responsiveness was adapted in neither country but challenged further in Sweden than in Denmark. Paradoxically, Denmark saw fewer adaptations to the liberal democratic ideas than Sweden yet appeared better prepared to protect lives during turbulent times. Our study suggests that liberal democracies must very carefully balance trade-offs between individual liberties and the protection of public health to preserve the core public ideas of constitutionality, parliamentarism, and public responsiveness.

Keywords: ideational robustness; Covid-19 pandemic; liberal democracy; Denmark; Sweden

The Covid-19 pandemic sparked unprecedented political responses in many countries, dramatically affecting societies, markets, and individual lives. The need to adopt far-reaching political interventions to curb the pandemic responded to what Ansell et al. (2020) term a “turbulent problem.” Substantial restrictions on individual rights and freedoms were enforced throughout the democratic world, with ensuing protests and demands for the preservation of liberal democratic ideas. In many countries, power was transferred from the legislature to the executive. Normal democratic processes and the protection of individual rights and freedoms were circumscribed, making some talk about the reappearance of the Leviathan (Runciman, 2021). These political responses entailed not only the reinvention of governance arrangements but also a rethinking of liberal democracy. The extent to which societies were able to retain the relevance and legitimacy of the liberal democratic ideas while also responding

efficiently to the pandemic remains unknown. This makes the pandemic a suitable event for studying the robustness of liberal democratic ideas.

This article focuses on two long-standing parliamentary liberal democracies: Denmark and Sweden. While we would expect the ideational robustness of liberal democracy during the pandemic to remain intact in the two countries, they responded differently to the pandemic. Denmark responded quite swiftly and decisively to limit the spread of the virus, whereas the Swedish response was slower and based on recommendations rather than restrictions. This means that the liberal democratic ideas in the two countries were challenged differently, possibly leading to different adaptations of the democratic ideas. This renders comparisons between the two countries highly interesting.

Our research question is: How did the political responses to the Covid-19 pandemic challenge key ideational features of liberal democracy in Denmark and Sweden, and to what extent were these ideas adapted to retain the relevance and legitimacy of liberal democracy throughout the pandemic? The overall aim of the paper is then to describe and normatively assess the political responses in terms of ideational robustness, neither to provide any causal explanation of the responses nor to gauge the responses' functional effectiveness.

This article tries to answer the research question by examining how three key ideational features of liberal democracy—constitutionality, parliamentarism, and public responsiveness—were challenged and adapted from March 2020 to May 2023, that is, approximately 1 year after most restrictions were dropped in both countries. We examine how government regulations resonated with key liberal democratic ideas of constitutionalism, whether parliament was excluded from insight in and influence on political decisions, and whether public reactions to government actions reinvigorated or threatened liberal democratic ideas. The limited period of the current study does not allow us to make any definite answers about the long-term impact on the ideational robustness of liberal democracy, but it does enable us to provide an indication of such.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows: We first present a theoretical framework outlining the key normative ideas underpinning liberal democracy in parliamentary systems. This is followed by an account of our method. The subsequent analysis is structured in three sections following the three ideational dimensions of liberal democracy. The final section presents the discussions and conclusions.

Ideational robustness and liberal democracy

Several public governance scholars have turned their attention to what it takes for public authorities to handle crises robustly (Ansell et al., 2020). The term “robustness” has long been used in a variety of academic disciplines. More recently, it has been introduced in public policy studies as both a descriptive and normative term to better grasp policy design under constantly changing pressures (Capano & Woo, 2017; Howlett et al., 2018). More precisely, robust governance has been defined as “the ability of one or more decision makers to uphold or realize a public agenda, function, or value in the face of the challenge and stress from turbulent events and processes through the flexible adaptation, agile modification, and pragmatic redirection of governance solutions” (Ansell et al., 2020: p. 259). Thus far, these studies have not focused on the role of ideas in relation to robustness. Studies, including those presented in this special issue, have started to consider the robustness of ideas and their role in the overall robustness of governance systems. (Carstensen et al., 2024) define the robustness of ideas in the introduction to this special issue as: “When ideas are adapted and innovated in ways that advance their ability to stay relevant when faced with turbulence.” Their definition of ideational robustness entails that the “adaptation and innovation of ideas [must] serve to preserve core public functions, goals and values” (Carstensen et al., 2024), implying that ideational robustness is a vital aspect of robust governance.

The present article focuses on the robustness of a set of core ideas in liberal democracy during the Covid-19 pandemic in Denmark and Sweden, namely, constitutionalism, parliamentarism, and responsiveness to the public. In many democratic countries, pandemic measures challenged these ideas by restricting rights and freedoms, introducing extralegal decisions, expanding government power, and silencing opposition voices (Bolleyer & Salát, 2021; Engler et al., 2021; Willison et al., 2022), although societies with longer-standing liberal democratic traditions were at lower risk of democratic backsliding (Engler et al., 2021; Lewkowicz et al., 2022). According to Goetz & Martinsen, (2021), the pandemic posed a “dual challenge” to liberal democracy by challenging both democratic principles and democratic performance. On the one hand, it has been argued that there is an increasing and worrying tendency in

the European Union (EU) to suspend constitutional procedures, at both the EU and the member state level, with reference to exceptional circumstances (Kreuder-Sonnen and White, 2022). Governments are using crisis, such as the pandemic, to reject societal reforms or push for constitutional changes. Such “emergency politics” risk eroding the legitimacy of the political system (White, 2019). On the other hand, if society or the population is exposed to an exceptional threat, the government has a duty to act in ways that may be exceptional to preserve core public functions, goals, and values. We argue that this dual challenge could be encountered in three ways: (1) by adhering to and retaining the accepted understanding of liberal democratic ideas, (2) by abandoning or breaking with these ideas to enable a more effective pandemic response, or (3) by adapting the ideas with a view to ensuring their relevance while simultaneously protecting other core goals and values, such as public health. The third avenue alone can be regarded as ideationally robust.

Although the constitutive ideas of liberal democracy change over time, for instance, the scope of who is regarded as the legitimate electorate expanded widely in most liberal democracies from the late nineteenth to the mid-twentieth century, legal and political scholars do not agree on whether temporary suspensions of certain existing laws and rights in exceptional situations (e.g., war, terrorism, fiscal collapse, or high-morbid pandemics) are legitimate (Ignatieff, 2005; Scheuerman, 2002). Some scholars argue that such exceptional government actions may be legitimate on the condition that decisions are sanctioned by *legislative* (e.g., parliamentary) majorities and that the introduction of laws that impede individual liberties are *temporary* and *specified* (rather than general) ways to secure the survival of the state and protect its population (Lazar, 2009; Zwitter, 2012). We use these three conditions as indicators of whether political change is ideationally robust.

The first liberal democratic idea studied, constitutionality, points to the liberal dimension of democracy by regulating the conduct of the rulers and their relationship to the ruled by law. The last two of these ideas resonate with the suggestion that democratic problem-solving should include the people in decision-making both indirectly via parliaments and more or less directly via, for instance, public debates and protests (Warren, 2017).

Constitutionality

In general, constitutionality, or *Rechtsstaat* principles—the normative idea that political rule must be sanctioned and tamed by a constitutional framework—is fundamental to liberal democracy. According to classical liberalists such as Adam Smith (Weingast, 2017 & John Stuart Mill, 1991), it is crucial that state power, whether endorsed by the wider public, be controlled and constrained by a set of hard-to-change constitutional rules. These rules safeguard individual citizens from property robbery, threats, and violent actions conducted either by other private citizens or by the state. At the face of it, constitutionality and its emphasis on a predictable and stable legal framework are at odds with adaptation and innovation. Obviously, the ideational value of constitutionalism is not that constitutions are immutable. Yet, to maintain the core ideational value, any changes of constitutions should adhere to those rules and procedures stipulated in the constitution.

Parliamentarism

Legislative assemblies are crucial to the idea of liberal democracy because they represent the voice of the people. Given that we study Denmark and Sweden, the focus here is on parliaments rather than other types of legislative assemblies. Parliamentarism implies that government rule must be accepted by the parliament and that it can hold the government accountable. Some scholars would also require the inclusion of parliament in deliberations and processes leading to government decisions and that the basis of the latter is transparent. Parliamentary inclusiveness entails deliberation between diverging political interests, that is, between government and opposition parties in parliament (Dryzek, 2000; Uhr, 1998). At minimum, this means that governments engage in deliberations and negotiations with opposition parties and, if possible, to accommodate their concerns (Beetham, 2006). Transparency enables the parliament to engage in meaningful deliberation with the government and to hold the latter to account for its actions (Moncrieffe, 1998). To do so, the parliament must have access to relevant information underpinning government decisions. In the case of the pandemic, much of this information was produced by expert agencies. If such agencies make decisions on matters concerning forced isolation, prevention of free movement, and mandatory vaccination, the ability of the parliament to engage in

meaningful deliberation may be compromised significantly, thereby undermining the ability of parliament to hold the government to account. Therefore, we will study not only the parliament–government relationship but also the relations to the relevant expert agencies.

Public responsiveness

Liberal democracies depend on an active civil society that is allowed to congregate and express their particular views and possible dissatisfaction with government decisions (Dahl, 1989). Governments are expected to pay serious attention to such public criticism, carefully weighing it against broader concerns concerning the public interest. Nevertheless, they are not obliged to accommodate protests by specific groups if these are seen as contrary to the public interest (Du Gay & Lopdrup-Hjorth, 2022: pp. 95–127). The extent to which a public discussion can be upheld during turbulent times is unclear. The issuance of threats and silencing attempts can be expected to increase and possibly compromise the freedom of speech. The ability to respond to such challenges is likely crucial for the robustness of a political system (Sørensen & Ansell, 2023). Turbulent times can also constitute a period in which the public articulates ideas that may either reinvigorate or threaten the three key features of liberal democracy that we identified. We look for public expressions that may reinvigorate or threaten liberal democracy together with eventual attempts by the government or other actors to silence such public expressions.

Method

This article is based on a comparative case study of Denmark and Sweden. The two countries may be considered representative of most similar systems. Both of them display strong welfare state features in which the state invests heavily in public health and welfare, corporatist traditions of institutionalized dialogue with private interest organizations in decision-making, multiparty parliamentary systems with long periods of minority governments requiring parliamentary cooperation, and political stability without any major constitutional upheaval since World War II (even longer for Sweden). During the pandemic, both Denmark and Sweden had Social Democrat–led minority governments (in Sweden including the Green Party). However, the Swedish Government for periods found very limited support in parliament, although decisions on the pandemic response were usually exempted. During the initial pandemic phase, the government was supported by two additional parties and tolerated by one, together reaching a parliamentary majority. In June 2021, disagreements over housing policies led to a vote of no confidence, which the government lost. It was later reinstated with an even thinner support.

In Denmark, the first round of closures in March 2020 was taken more or less unilaterally by the prime minister (PM)'s office (Christensen, 2021). Thereafter, an ad hoc action group was formed with key ministers (health, finance, and justice) who had two overall tasks: curbing the spread of the virus and deploying financial packages to help the business sector. In March 2021, this group was replaced by the National Epidemic Commission made up of ministries and representatives of the regions and the municipalities (Interview, 2023a). In Sweden, there was no commission gathering actors from different political levels. Instead, the regions and municipalities had to rely on the normal communication channels. Initially, the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs took the lead, in close contact with the Public Health Agency and the National Board of Health and Welfare. During the pandemic, several institutionalized and ad hoc groups came to be used for coordination within the government office and with national agencies (SOU, 2022).

In terms of pandemic policies, both countries' responses were mild in a global perspective, avoiding closures and restrictions on movement (Hale et al., 2021; see also online [Supplementary material S1](#) and [S2](#)). Compared, for instance, to the Netherlands, the Danish and Swedish interventions were much less intrusive (online [Supplementary material S2](#)). Notwithstanding this relative similarity, the two countries responded to the pandemic rather differently, especially during the first wave. Initially, Denmark introduced a comprehensive set of restrictions, including the lockdown of large parts of the education sector, mandatory testing at workplaces, and mandatory mask-wearing in public spaces. The Swedish strategy was based on recommendations, with restrictions introduced first during the second wave. Although the countries' policies became more similar, significant differences remained, for example, concerning school closings, face masks, testing, and public gatherings (Table 1; online [Supplementary Table S1](#); online [Supplementary material S2](#)). Other differences were that the Swedish response was expert-led

Table 1. Pandemic regulations during the first and second waves (only new measures mentioned).

Country	First wave (March–April 2020)	Second wave (October 2020–March 2021)
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closing of borders • Public assembly of more than 10 persons prohibited (excluding political demonstrations) • Temporary closure of schools (above fourth grade) • Temporary closure of many private businesses • Economic support to companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ban on travels from risk regions • Mandatory testing and mask-wearing in (indoor) public spaces • Doubling the sanctions for actions obstructing the public authorities' efforts to curb the pandemic • Online or outdoor teaching • Mandatory "Corona Passport" (vaccination or negative test) in most indoor public spaces
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ban on travels from risk regions • Public assembly of more than 500 persons (initially prohibited; later reduced to 50 persons (including political demonstrations) • Temporary closure of schools (above fourth grade) • No mandatory closure of private businesses • Requirement on restaurants to have seated service and distance between tables • Support to companies and workers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prohibiting public assemblies above eight people (including political demonstrations) • Various limitations on the number of people at different types of assemblies (e.g., religious meetings) • Limits on the number of people in shops, restaurants, training facilities, etc. • Schools kept open (temporary closures possible for schools with many Covid-19 infections) • Vaccination not mandatory (recommendation for those above 12 years) • Introduction of vaccine certificates (not widely used)

to a greater extent and that the Danish was more hierarchical (Christensen & Lægheid, 2020). The pandemic also hit the countries differently, with Sweden initially suffering very high mortality rates (online [Supplementary material S3](#)) and a heavily strained health care system. The cumulative confirmed that Covid-19 deaths in Denmark are among the lowest in Europe, whereas the initial weak performance of Sweden was later balanced, leading to mortality rates below the European average (Hale et al., 2021; online [Supplementary material S4](#)). The variation summarized in [Table 1](#) provides opportunity to study how different government crisis responses affected the ideational foundation of liberal democracy and how adaptations to democratic ideas supported the ideational robustness of liberal democracy in two most similar systems.

A wide range of public documents support our analysis. Regarding the idea of constitutionality, we examine government and parliamentary documents, regulations, and public health documents. We examine the extent to which the government respected the constitution, laws, and regulations, what changes were made in these, and if and how the idea of constitutionality was adapted.

Regarding parliamentarism, we study parliamentary debate minutes and statements (both government and leading opposition parties) in national newspapers. We examine the extent to which the pandemic shifted the balance between the parliament, government, and national health agencies. We examine the extent to which the respective health agencies provided access to knowledge to the national parliaments and the extent to which, formally or informally, power was transferred to these agencies or the government.

Finally, the democratic idea of responsiveness to civil society voices is studied via national newspapers and government and parliamentary documents. We look for two things: first the civil society responses to government regulations seeking to mitigate the Covid-19 virus in Denmark and Sweden; second, we examine whether some of the protests articulated new understandings of the liberal democratic ideas stipulated earlier. We also examine how governments responded to such public expressions.

Constitutional ideas in action

The Danish constitution does not provide any legal basis for declaring a state of emergency that may suspend the usual parliamentary process. The pandemic therefore had to be governed through the conventional legislative procedures (i.e., through parliament). In March 2020, the government adopted several political interventions seeking to curb the pandemic. The existing legislation allowed for some of them, while others required new legislation. Like most other countries, Denmark already had legislation pertaining to epidemics prior to the outbreak of Covid-19 (LBK nr 1026 af 1 October 2019). Given the extensive powers that this legislation provided to public health authorities and the room it provides for issuing subsidiary regulations, it is hardly surprising that it is only the Covid-19 pandemic that required limited amendments. To prevent the spread of dangerous and contagious diseases, the legislation enabled the so-called epidemic commissions to force citizens suspected of being infected to medical testing, treatment, and isolation, to inoculate specific groups by force, and finally to reject people from entering Denmark if they refuse medical treatment or isolation. With one important exception (see later), the government was able to remain within the legal parameters. The temporary closure of the Danish borders, the closure of schools, day cares and certain businesses, mandatory testing, and the restrictions on public assembly all took place within the ambit of the existing epidemic legislation.

The government decision in November 2020 to cull all mink in Denmark was a major exception to the general constitutional and legal compliance. The decision had no legal basis and constituted a clear break with the inviolability of private property. Earlier efforts to prevent the spread of the virus between animals and to farmers and their families had been unsuccessful. The head of Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Kåre Mølbak, stated at a press conference together with the PM that “The worst case scenario is that we get a pandemic starting all over in Denmark” (Government press meeting, 2020). At the same meeting, the PM explained that all Danish mink had to be culled because the rapid viral mutations in them could contribute to immunity to the existing vaccines. Shortly thereafter, it became apparent that there was no legal basis for this. Most opposition parties were furious, demanding that the decision be scrutinized by an independent commission, which was subsequently established (Christensen et al., 2021). Nevertheless, a few months later, a parliamentary majority voted in favor of adopting a law legalizing the culling of mink. Moreover, there was no parliamentary agreement on toppling the entire government; only the Minister of Food and Agriculture had to resign. The independent Commission Inquiry concluded that the PM was unaware of the lacking legal basis of the decision (Granskningskommissionen, 2021). Instead, the Commission found that a police chief and the top civil servants advising the PM and the Minister of Agriculture had displayed gross negligence by failing to ensure the legality. Still, these top civil servants were all ultimately exonerated. Some legal scholars regard this exoneration of the PM and civil servants as a violation of the constitutional principle according to which those in power are held responsible for the abuse of power (Geist, 2023). In brief, the illegal culling of mink seriously challenged the idea of constitutionalism. The lacking consequences for the involved government politicians and leading civil servants could suggest a potentially enduring threat to legal accountability. While it would be wrong to conclude that the normative ideas of constitutionality and legality have been permanently undermined based on a single incident, the idea of constitutionality did not seem very robust.

As in Denmark, the Swedish constitution provides no legal basis for enforcing a peacetime state of emergency. The government initially utilized existing delegations of power to make decisions, including restrictions on the right to assembly and a ban on visits to nursing homes. To enable a lockdown, the government made a request to the parliament in April 2020 to increase its mandate (Swedish Government, 2020), which triggered intense debate and protests from the opposition. As the government lacked majority support, the result was circumscribed in its scope and timeframe. The amendment to the Communicable Diseases Act was temporary (expiring end of June), and all government decisions required immediate parliamentary acknowledgment (Swedish Parliament, 2020). Although never used, the amendment was subsequently criticized for being too general (SOU, 2022).

During the second wave, in early January 2021, the government requested the renewal of its ability to restrict individual rights, including close activities. This resulted in the Pandemic Act. Although the government defined the scope and timeframe of the interventions (Swedish Government, 2021),

political debate forced it to adjust the bill in two ways before it was even presented: an earlier expiration date and a 1-week (instead of two) respite before parliamentary approval of decisions. Aside from the right-wing populist Sweden Democrats, the parties all agreed that restrictions on individual rights and freedoms were both necessary and legitimate (Swedish Parliament, 2021a). How to balance restrictions, however, remained unclear. In particular, several of the opposition parties saw the need to restrict private enterprises, like shops and training facilities, but wanted to avoid restricting trade (Swedish Parliament, 2021b). Although the government shared this concern, the opposition was not content (Kristersson & Svantesson, 2021; Swedish Parliament, 2021a). Throughout the pandemic, the restrictions on the freedom of trade did not achieve the same legitimacy among the opposition as the restrictions on the right to assembly. Despite such concerns, the parliament approved the Pandemic Act. This was made possible by the Act being temporary and well-defined in terms of its scope, circumscribed by three principles: government action was only allowed to prevent the spread of Covid-19; measures needed to be proportionate; and measures should consider the nature of different activities, preventing blanket restrictions covering all activities. The Pandemic Act was based on an ideational reinterpretation of what was deemed legitimate in Swedish liberal democracy and understood as necessary to ensure continued public functions, goals, and values. Except for how to adapt freedom of trade, the liberal democratic idea of constitutionality proved ideationally robust.

Parliamentarian ideas in action

Attempts at “executive aggrandizements” have been present in many European countries, (temporary) decreasing the power of parliaments. Beyond such attempts, this section will focus on the work of the public health authorities and how they contributed to parliament with expert knowledge. This is an important aspect of parliamentarism, as the ability of parliaments to make pandemic decisions and to evaluate the efficiency of government policies and ultimately to hold governments accountable relied on the access to expert knowledge.

In Denmark, two public health authorities were key during the epidemic: the Danish Health Authority (Sundhedsstyrelsen) and SSI. Both operate under the auspices of the Ministry of Health, and both function as expert advisers for the Ministry. The main difference between the two organizations is that the Danish Health Authority provides advice and contributes to the implementation of government decisions. Apart from providing advice, the SSI is mainly concerned with research on and the monitoring of diseases in Denmark, not least epidemic-level diseases. This setup has one important consequence. They report to the Ministry of Health, that is, the government, not parliament. Thus, even if much of the knowledge produced by the two organizations is published, much of their specific advice and recommendations will only be given to parliament if the Ministry of Health deems this opportune.

This strong ministerial control over information has been the target of considerable parliamentary dispute during the pandemic. For instance, when two medical researchers who had advised the government during earlier pandemics complained about the lack of access to the epidemiological data produced by SSI, the leading opposition party immediately addressed their critique (Kildegaard, 2020). Unsurprisingly, the opposition was particularly upset over what they saw as inadequate access to SSI’s virological assessments informing the decision to cull all mink in Denmark. Following the decision, the opposition forced the government to organize a public hearing where the heads of both the Danish Health Authority and SSI were queried about the evidence behind the decision. Finally, the government has been accused of exerting political pressure on the kind of advice formulated by the public health authorities. Their advice is supposed to be based exclusively on scientific expertise, not on what is politically opportune for the government. However, the report made by the independent commission examining the extralegal culling of mink revealed how the SSI was under strong pressure from the PM’s Office to formulate its risk analysis in ways that would endorse the government decision to cull all Danish mink (Granskningskommissionen, 2021). In sum, the pandemic seriously challenged the robustness of the idea that parliamentarism should provide the opposition with access to the information supporting government decisions. Given that the Danish central government administration is generally less obliged to disclose the information underpinning its decisions than in Sweden (Jørgensen, 2014: pp. 173, 248), its reluctance to share information during the pandemic is hardly surprising. Still, this lack of disclosure of expert knowledge posed a serious challenge to the ideas of parliamentarism. The limited public access to the interactions between ministers, their ministries, and their agencies

cannot be seen as an ideational adaptation, as it was a feature of the Danish central administration both prior to and following the pandemic. However, the ability to provide robust parliamentary solutions to future crises may be impeded by this lacking transparency, a key ideational value of liberal democracy.

In Sweden, the existing Communicable Diseases Act, during specific circumstances under pandemics, grants the Public Health Agency—and in some cases regional medical officers—authority to enforce quarantines and lockdown of limited areas. The Public Health Agency, however, relied on advice and recommendations to the public based on the focus of the Act on individual responsibility (SOU, 2022). Instead, the parliament and later the government made the formal decisions restricting individual rights and freedoms, in accordance with the norm that the parliament has to decide on restrictions on rights and freedoms. However, during the first wave, the government acted almost exclusively on the request of the Agency to curb the spread of the virus (see SOU, 2022). The large, informal influence of the Public Health Agency on decisions related to the spread could imply information shortages for the opposition in parliament, as the Agency reported to the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs. However, the opposition parties did not complain about a general lack of transparency. The initially daily (later twice-weekly) press briefings held by the Public Health Agency might have contributed to this.

What the opposition parties instead complained about was the government's lack of transparency and foresight when presenting bills to the parliament. The parliament had agreed to speed up the decision-making process, which shortened the processing of government bills to a few days. On several occasions, however, the opposition parties criticized the government for presenting bills to the parliament so late that proper debate was impossible. This was especially the case for the Pandemic Act, where the opposition fiercely criticized the government for lacking foresight and unnecessarily jeopardizing democratic processes (Kristersson et al., 2020; Swedish Parliament, 2020). A further point of opposition criticism was the lack of government leadership. The opposition increasingly demanded swifter, more decisive action and wanted the government to stop hiding behind its experts (TT, 2020; SVT Nyheter, 2020). The same type of criticism was voiced in the public debate (e.g., Ahlenius, 2020; Carlsson et al., 2020; Nerbrand, 2020). By relying on experts, the opposition argued the government was avoiding accountability. This was one of the reasons for opposition demands for an immediate, independent inquiry (Kristersson & Strömmer, 2020). Although the parliament, through the Pandemic Act, accepted an adaptation of the idea of parliamentarism through its delegation of power from the parliament to the government and the Public Health Agency, the parliament limited the ideational adaptation by forcing the government to circumscribe the delegation of power quite significantly, in terms of both scope and timeframes, as already discussed, and by protecting the importance of accountability.

The ideas of parliamentarism are still debated after the pandemic. In November 2023, a parliamentary committee presented recommendations (SOU, 2023), including a revision of the constitution to allow for a wider transfer of power from the parliament to the government during

peacetime crises. However, government decisions under such extraordinary circumstances should be temporary, specified, and shortly approved by the parliament. The recommendations provide evidence of more long-term adaptations to the ideas of parliamentarism, accepted by all but one of the participating party representatives.

Ideas of public responsiveness in action

This section examines, first, the civil society responses to government regulations seeking to mitigate Covid-19 in Denmark and Sweden. Second, we examine whether some of the protests articulated new understandings of democracy that goes against one or more of the liberal democratic principles stipulated earlier

Civil society responses

Throughout the pandemic, the Danish government enjoyed consistent, high levels of trust and support for how it handled the pandemic (Nielsen & Lindvall, 2021). This may have meant that the government saw little reason for being very attentive to various emerging civil society criticisms. Moreover, the regions and the municipalities were directly represented in the National Epidemic Commission. This local government representation allowed for extensive feedback on practical concerns, often expressed by patients, relatives, teachers, and parents over the pandemic regulations pertaining to the hospitals, eldercare, and schools. Still, while the Danish government in general enjoyed high levels of support,

some civil society actors did protest against the pandemic regulations. Most of these protests were legal. For instance, three or four minor groups persistently organized demonstrations criticizing the mask mandate and claiming that Covid-19 did not exist (Stavnsbjerg, 2020). Moreover, on several instances, the two major Danish tabloids criticized the consistency of the specific regulations and the unclear evidence supporting them (e.g., Dyrby, 2020; Madsen, 2021).

The relatively few illegal protests that did occur included farmers blocking the authorities' access to test mink farms for coronavirus and demonstrations organized in the major cities (Jeppesen, 2021; Jørgensen, 2020). They also included Men in Black, a social media-based group that organized several demonstrations from fall 2020 to spring 2021. At least one demonstration resulted in violent actions and arrests (Olsen, 2021). Finally, Danish government ministers and the heads of the public health authorities were subjected to various forms of hate speech, and the PM was the target of physical threats (Københavns Politi, 2021). Much of the hate speech was delivered via either the social media or personally addressed e-mails. Several medical experts and local municipal workers assisting in testing and vaccination were also subjected to hate speech (Interview, 2023b).

From the onset of the pandemic, the Swedish Government did not enjoy the same level of public trust and support as in Denmark, with a higher polarization between left- and right-wing voters' trust (Nielsen & Lindvall, 2021). The affective polarization between those supporting the Swedish strategy and those advocating more restrictions was high (Flores et al., 2022). Those advocating stricter restrictions, like full school closings and face mask requirements, were initially the most vocal (e.g., Carlsson, 2020). Public resistance to the restrictions, including through illegal demonstrations, first started to form after the introduction of the Pandemic Act. With few exceptions, the demonstrations gathered less than 500 participants and received limited public support (Dahlberg, 2021; Magnusson et al., 2021; Nyman & Näslund, 2021). Many of the demonstrations were led by the Freedom Movement, gathering those skeptical about elites (Dalsbro, 2021).

Hate speech and threats were directed at those participating in the public debate, silencing some actors (Svensson, 2020; Sörbring, 2021; Trysell, 2021). One example of the harsh tone in the debate is the accusations voiced in public radio against Media Watchdogs Sweden, a social media group. The broadcast claimed the group was spreading lies about the Swedish strategy, trying to influence the image of Sweden abroad (SR, 2021). The group later defended the freedom of speech, highlighting the negative impact of "fake news" on democracy (Nylander, 2021). The government mostly remained neutral to the challenges facing the liberal democratic values of open and respectful debate. When it raised the issue, it was to defend the existing understanding of these ideas (SVT Nyheter, 2021; TT, 2021). While the restrictions on the right to assemble were accompanied by an ideational shift, which was seen as legitimate by politicians and large parts of the electorate, this was not the case for freedom of speech. As such, the disciplining tendencies in the public debate must be seen as the most serious challenge to the ideational robustness of liberal democratic ideas in the Swedish case.

New understandings of democracy

In Denmark, the aforementioned Men in Black tried to formulate a new understanding of what a democracy should look like. Their manifesto called for a rethinking of the entire political system (Thorup, 2021) and envisages a society with less distance between citizens and the power and where all citizens should be allowed to make their own choice, including more frequent use of referendums to spur more direct democracy, as in Switzerland. Finally, they wanted Denmark to seize its allegiance with the EU and the World Health Organization, instead forming a union with Norway and Sweden. Other groups protesting against the Covid-19 regulations pointed to some of the same issues as Men in Black, albeit without the same comprehensive societal vision. While the Men in Black emphasized their struggle as being more about more direct freedom for the people than fighting the Covid-19 regulations (Terp, 2021), their activities and the public attention they received seem to have withered rapidly after restrictions were lifted in 2021. It should also be noted that no parliamentarians have shown any support for the movement. In sum, Denmark has seen quite substantive protests from civil society groups in both rural and urban areas. While all have in some way pointed to what they see as government violations of individual freedoms, the activities of these groups have not been coordinated. More importantly, only one group formulated a vision of a different form of democracy, and it did not lead to a more widespread adaptation of the democratic ideas.

The Swedish equivalent to Men in Black was the Freedom Movement, which shared the focus on returning power to the people (Dalsbro, 2021) but lacked any manifesto of a democratic alternative. The movement grew rapidly in 2021 but found limited support among the electorate and established political parties alike. An alternative understanding of democracy, in which only “real experts” were seen as legitimate debaters, took form in the public debate. Experts were judged by others, including by the Public Health Agency, as not holding legitimate knowledge (see, e.g., Sörbring, 2021). Similar to hate speech and threats, these tendencies led to a silencing of critical voices and challenged the normal understandings of the public debate. The government and parliament generally ignored these tendencies.

See Table 2 for a summary of the analysis.

Table 2. Challenges to and adaptations of liberal democratic ideas during the pandemic.

Liberal Democratic Ideas	Denmark	Sweden
Constitutionality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restrictions on rights and freedoms were accompanied by adaptations to the ideas of constitutionality that were temporary, specific, and seen as legitimate by the political opposition. The illegal culling of mink seriously challenged the idea of constitutionalism, not least because of the limited consequences for the responsible government politicians. Unclear whether this ideational adaptation is temporary, but the idea of constitutionality did not seem very robust given the lack of post hoc sanctions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restrictions on rights and freedoms were accompanied by adaptations to the ideas of constitutionality that were temporary, specific, and seen as legitimate by the political opposition (except for restrictions on the freedom of trade). The idea of constitutionality proved robust.
Parliamentarism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shifts in the idea of parliamentarism concerning the speed of parliamentary work and minor adaptations to the legitimate size of delegated power. Lacking disclosure of expert knowledge challenged the idea of transparency and political accountability—no adaptations made. The parliament did not accept permanent legislative changes to short-circuit parliament. The idea of parliamentarism was robust. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shift in the idea of parliamentarism concerning the speed of parliamentary work and the size and area of the power delegated from parliament to government and public agencies. The parliament limited the adaptation by circumscribing the scope and timeframe of the legislative shift. The idea of parliamentarism was robust.
Public responsiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong popular support for the government, but substantive protests from minor civil society groups against mandatory masks, testing, and vaccination. One group formulated a vision of more direct democracy. Political dismissal of this alternative vision of democracy. No ideational adaptation was made. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The restrictions on the right to assemble and the silencing tendencies in the public debate affected opportunities to make one’s voice heard and the government’s ability to be responsive to the public. The restrictions on the right to assemble were accompanied by an adaptation of its ideational foundation (constitutionalism), whereas this was not the case for challenges to the freedom of speech. No ideational adaptation was made.

Conclusion

This article has analyzed and compared how the political interventions seeking to curb the spread of the coronavirus affected the ideas of liberal democracy in Denmark and Sweden. It also examined whether these ideas were adapted to retain their legitimacy while still enabling efficient pandemic management. The analysis focused on three key ideas: constitutionality, parliamentarism, and the public response to government actions.

Our study found that the ideas of liberal democracy in the two countries were partly robust. Paradoxically, Denmark saw less adaptations of the liberal democratic ideas than Sweden yet appeared more prepared for turbulent times, as the Danish system seemed better equipped at acting decisively to protect the health of its citizens.

The idea of constitutionalism was adapted in both countries. The extralegal culling of mink in Denmark stands out as clearly challenging the core ideational value of constitutionalism. Although this constitutional breach was vehemently criticized by the parliamentary opposition, it had a very limited (negative) impact on the high level of public trust enjoyed by the government, indicating a public support for the measure. Sweden saw a shift in constitutional ideas, notably restrictions on political demonstrations. Such restrictions on rights and freedoms were mostly seen as necessary and acceptable as they were temporary and specific. The idea of constitutionalism, therefore, proved to be robust in both countries, except for the Danish culling of mink.

The idea of parliamentarism saw substantial, albeit temporary and specific, adaptations in both countries. The Danish and Swedish parliaments temporarily accepted accelerated legislative processes and the delegation of rather far-reaching powers to public health agencies. In Denmark, the parliament rejected a legislative proposal involving a permanent shift of power to the government during pandemics. No such attempt was made in Sweden, which instead saw a limited ideational shift as the parliament accepted a temporary and highly specified delegation of decision-making power. In Denmark, the parliamentary opposition was highly critical of their limited access to information from the national agencies, as this information was controlled by the government. This did not seem to be an issue in Sweden. The parliaments in both countries defended the prevailing ideas of parliamentarism, although accepting some adaptations, proving the ideas to be robust. The exception is the restrictions to information from national agencies experienced by the Danish parliamentary opposition.

The idea of public responsiveness saw substantial changes in neither country. The Swedish Government's possibility to be responsive to the public was reduced more than in Denmark, as the affective polarization in the Swedish public debate, combined with silencing tendencies and the drastically decreased number of allowed participants in demonstrations, made it harder to voice dissenting opinions. Thus, the lack of adaptations to the ideas of public responsiveness was thus more challenging in Sweden than in Denmark.

Finally, it may be worth discussing the generalizing potential of the present study. On the one hand, the Danish and Swedish pandemic responses differ from those found in many other liberal democracies by way of their high level of trust in government, a fairly high health service capacity, and an absence of emergency clauses in the constitution. On the other hand, the trade-offs between liberal democratic ideals and the responsibility to protect the population under duress are largely the same as in other parliamentary democracies.

First, there is a trade-off between, on the one hand, constitutional ideals on individual liberties and the rule of law and, on the other, an effective crisis response. All democratic systems face the same trade-off between protecting constitutional ideals and effective crisis response, leading to a risk of either adapting ideals so far that they eventually break or adapting them too little, leading to an inadequate crisis response. Both Denmark and Sweden choose to adapt constitutional ideas only limitedly and temporary (with one exception). Therefore, a larger adaptation to protect lives, implying, for example, an acceptance of temporary restrictions in the movement of citizens, might have been possible. However, it is neither possible to determine the optimal trade-off in these cases, nor is such a trade-off likely to be defined that holds for all democratic systems. Rather, this balance depends on contextual features, like the level of trust in government, the capacity of the health services, eventual emergency clauses in the constitution, etc. To enable a balanced response that allows for both the adaptation of liberal democratic ideas and a proportionate crisis management, broadly accepted ideational adaptations that enable specific and temporary restrictions to individual civil liberties and other constitutional principles are crucial.

Second, there is a trade-off between the power of the parliament and the executive's ability to take swift and comprehensive action. Countries differ regarding the extent to which the executive during a crisis can take actions without parliamentary support. Both the Danish and the Swedish governments lack such possibilities. In parliamentary democracies, this possibility is dependent on specific rules governing the relation between the government and parliament, which may vary between countries, as well as on the extent of support that the government holds in parliament. A strong support could, in principle, give the government a *carte blanche* to disregard the parliamentary opposition. Such actions could limit the acceptability of adaptations to ideas of parliamentarianism essential for an effective crisis management. The same dynamic also pertains to the dissemination of agency knowledge. If governmental control over agency knowledge is high, transparency might be weak, leading to a diffuse (i.e., under-specified) scope of the extended government power. As in the Danish case, this can lead to the parliament resisting the executive's decisions and legislative proposals. A high transparency, instead, enables the parliament to balance its power against the executive's ability to act, as witnessed in the Swedish case.

Finally, there is a trade-off between keeping channels for public voices and concerns open versus restricting them to limit the spread of the disease and maintain public order. This trade-off pertains both to public protests over closures and to civil servants' concerns over how to secure hospital services, eldercare, schooling, and business. Given the relatively high levels of public trust in authorities in both Denmark and Sweden, it is very difficult to generalize the findings to other countries. Without such trust, it is probably more difficult to strike a balance between the right to public expression and the concern for ensuring public health and order. That said, it seems fair to assume that to manage these trade-offs, governments in all liberal democracies are most likely better off by being transparent about the limitations of available expert evidence and being open about uncertainties this implies for decision-making. While such transparency will not make conspiracy theories and polarization go away, it will create the conditions for an enlightened public debate about the pros and cons of the possible political responses to a turbulent situation.

Supplementary material

[Supplementary material](#) is available online at *Music Therapy Perspectives*.

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Conflict of interest

None declared.

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